

Case Report

Jugular-Applied Coherent Low Level Laser Therapy Modulates Mitochondrial Gene Networks Linked to Healthy Aging: A Longitudinal Pilot Study

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Abstract

Healthy aging is supported by the maintenance of mitochondrial function, cellular energy regulation, and redox balance. Low-level laser therapy (LLLT) has been shown to affect mitochondrial bioenergetics and downstream transcriptional pathways, although molecular evidence in aged companion animals remains limited. This pilot study investigated whether jugular applied coherent laser LLLT was associated with systemic changes in the expression of mitochondrial and energy related genes in geriatric dogs. Five geriatric Beagles (9–13 years old), including some with stable chronic comorbidities, were treated with a wearable coherent laser device applied to the jugular region for 5 sessions per week over 2 weeks, for a total of 10 treatments. Whole blood samples were obtained at baseline (T₀), day 14 (T₁), and day 28 (T₂). Relative expressions of PPARGC1A, TFAM, SIRT1, SIRT3, and PRKAA1 were assessed by RT-qPCR. Median gene expression changes from baseline were positive across all five mitochondrial aging related targets at post treatment (T₁) and 28 day follow up (T₂), though responses were heterogeneous, three of five animals showed meaningful upregulation while two showed minimal or no change. These findings suggest that jugular applied coherent laser LLLT may generate a preliminary systemic molecular signal consistent with activation of mitochondrial biogenesis and energy sensing pathways relevant to healthy aging in geriatric dogs.

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Introduction

Aging is increasingly understood as a systems level biological process driven by interacting hallmarks: mitochondrial dysfunction, altered nutrient sensing, impaired stress resistance, chronic lowgrade inflammation, and reduced regenerative capacity [1]. Among these, mitochondrial decline is especially central because it links energy production, redox homeostasis, inflammatory signaling, and cellular resilience across virtually every organ system [2]. In both humans and dogs, aging is associated with diminished mitochondrial efficiency, altered oxidative metabolism, and reduced systemic adaptability to metabolic stress [3,4].

Five molecular regulators are central to these processes and serve as the gene panel for this study. PPARGC1A encodes PGC-1 α , the master regulator of mitochondrial biogenesis and oxidative metabolism [5]. TFAM is essential for mitochondrial DNA transcription, replication, and maintenance [6]. SIRT1 and SIRT3 are NAD⁺-dependent deacetylases involved in metabolic regulation, redox balance, and mitochondrial quality control [7,8]. PRKAA1, encoding the catalytic α -1 subunit of AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), is a key cellular energy sensor that integrates metabolic stress and promotes adaptive responses [9]. Together, these five genes constitute a biologically coherent network directly relevant to mitochondrial health, cellular resilience, and systemic aging biology.

Low Level Laser Therapy (LLLT) uses non thermal low intensity coherent light to modulate biological function. Proposed mechanisms include changes in mitochondrial bioenergetics, transient shifts in reactive oxygen species and nitric oxide signaling, and downstream effects on ATP production, transcriptional regulation, and inflammatory [10-12]. Critically, when LLLT is applied to a highly vascular region such as the jugular area, the intervention has the potential to influence not only local tissue but also circulating components including mitochondria and mitochondria derived vesicles present in blood [13,14]. This raises the possibility that jugular applied LLLT could act as a systemic intervention by modulating circulating mitochondrial cargo as blood transits the illuminated site.

There are no known molecular studies examining aging related mitochondrial pathways in geriatric dogs using wearable laser formats. The present pilot study was designed to evaluate feasibility and to explore whether jugular applied coherent LLLT is associated with longitudinal changes in whole blood gene expression across a panel of mitochondrial and energy sensing markers in geriatric Beagle dogs. We hypothesized that LLLT would be associated with directional upregulation of PPARGC1A, TFAM, SIRT1, SIRT3, and PRKAA1, consistent with activation of pathways relevant to systemic healthy aging.

Materials And Methods

Animals

Five geriatric Beagle dogs aged 9–13 years were included. All animals were clinically stable at enrollment. Dogs were assigned the following study identification codes: FTB01, TNH02, GUR03, POA04, and LUF05. Some dogs had chronic but compensated comorbidities. TNH02 and LUF05 had chronic conditions reportedly consistent with diabetes mellitus, hypercapnia, and ehrlichiosis, which were described as controlled and clinically stable during the study period.

Low Level Laser Therapy (LLLT) Intervention

Animals received LLLT using the Erchonia MitoCollar, a wearable coherent laser device positioned over the jugular region. The device emitted 7.5 mW laser light using a proprietary pulsed frequency. Treatment was administered for 20 minutes per session, five times per week for two consecutive weeks, for a total of 10 sessions. The total energy delivered per treatment was 9 J. Device application followed manufacturer recommendations.

Data collection

Blood samples were collected at T0, T1, and T2. RNA was extracted and analyzed by RT-qPCR. Relative expressions of PPARGC1A, TFAM, SIRT1, SIRT3, and PRKAA1 were quantified after normalization to validated reference genes. Whole blood gene expression was selected as the measurement readout specifically because it provides a systemic, organism level molecular readout that is not restricted to a single tissue.

Data analysis

Given the exploratory and hypothesis generating nature of this study, no formal statistical analysis was applied. Data are presented descriptively, with interpretation focused on the direction and magnitude of individual longitudinal change within and across animals.

Results

Cohort Level Directional Trends

Across the cohort, median directional changes from baseline to post treatment were positive for all five genes examined with a cohort wide pattern that, measured in whole blood, reflects a systemic molecular response. For PPARGC1A, median change was +0.290 from T0 to T1 and +0.240 from T0 to T2. For TFAM, median change was +0.210 from T0 to T1 and +0.150 from T0 to T2. SIRT1 increased by a median of +0.150 at T1 and +0.080 at T2. SIRT3 increased by a median of +0.190 at T1 and +0.160 at T2. PRKAA1 increased by a median of +0.260 at T1 and +0.210 at T2.

Inter-Individual Response Patterns

Response patterns differed substantially among dogs. FTB01 and POA04 showed the clearest molecular response. In both animals, PPARGC1A and TFAM rose substantially at T1 and remained above baseline at T2. These changes were accompanied by moderate increases in SIRT1, SIRT3, and PRKAA1, demonstrating coordinated upregulation across the full panel of genes involved in mitochondrial biogenesis, mitochondrial maintenance, and cellular energy sensing. This coordinated pattern across five mechanistically distinct genes in the same animals is notable because it is inconsistent with random expression noise and suggests genuine engagement of an interconnected mitochondrial health pathway.

GUR03 exhibited a moderate but internally consistent response, with increases across all five genes at T1 that persisted, though slightly attenuated, at T2. In contrast, TNH02 remained largely stable across the panel, showing only minimal fluctuations over time. LUF05 showed little evidence of a favorable molecular response and demonstrated a mild downward trend in selected markers, including PPARGC1A, SIRT1, and PRKAA1.

Gene Specific Observations

For PPARGC1A, the most notable increases were observed in FTB01 (0.73 to 1.41 at T1; 1.36 at T2) and POA04 (0.65 to 1.33 at T1; 1.28 at T2). TFAM followed a similar pattern, increasing in FTB01 (0.91 to 1.34; 1.29) and POA04 (0.76 to 1.35; 1.30), with GUR03 also showing a moderate rise (1.07 to 1.28; 1.22). For SIRT1 and SIRT3, FTB01, GUR03, and POA04 exhibited modest increases at T1 with partial persistence at T2, whereas TNH02 and LUF05 changed minimally. PRKAA1 showed the same general structure of response, with the strongest increases in FTB01 and POA04 and an intermediate rise in GUR03 [Tables 1-5] [Figures 1-5].

Animal ID	Baseline (T0)	Post treatment (T1)	28 day Follow up (T2)
FTB01	0.73	1.41	1.36
TNH02	1.04	1.01	1.02
GUR03	0.87	1.16	1.11
POA04	0.65	1.33	1.28
LUF05	0.96	0.93	0.9

Table 1: PPARGC1A Individual Relative Expression Values.

Figure 1: PPARGC1A Individual Response Trajectories.

Animal ID	Baseline (T0)	Post treatment (T1)	28 day Follow up (T2)
FTB01	0.91	1.34	1.29
TNH02	1.01	0.99	0.98
GUR03	1.07	1.28	1.22
POA04	0.76	1.35	1.3
LUF05	1.12	1.1	1.09

Table 2: TFAM Individual Relative Expression Values.

Figure 2: TFAM Individual Response Trajectories.

Animal ID	Baseline (T0)	Post treatment (T1)	28-day Follow up (T2)
FTB01	1.13	1.28	1.21
TNH02	1.11	1.09	1.1
GUR03	0.96	1.18	1.16
POA04	0.88	1.24	1.21
LUF05	1.02	0.97	0.96

Table 3: SIRT1 Individual Relative Expression Values.

Figure 3: SIRT1 Individual Response Trajectories.

Animal ID	Baseline (T0)	Post treatment (T1)	28 day Follow up (T2)
FTB01	0.95	1.26	1.19
TNH02	0.75	0.78	0.76
GUR03	0.98	1.17	1.14
POA04	1.03	1.29	1.25
LUF05	0.76	0.74	0.75

Table 4: SIRT3 Individual Response Trajectories.

Figure 4: SIRT3 Individual Response Trajectories.

Animal ID	Baseline (T0)	Post treatment (T1)	28 day Follow up (T2)
FTB01	1.14	1.4	1.35
TNH02	0.85	0.86	0.86
GUR03	0.93	1.19	1.14
POA04	1.05	1.37	1.29
LUF05	0.83	0.78	0.8

Table 5: PRKAA1 Individual Relative Expression Values.

Figure 5: PRKAA1 Individual Response Trajectories.

Discussion

The five genes examined in this study were selected because each encodes a protein with a distinct and well-established role in the biology of healthy aging. PPARGC1A encodes a protein commonly known as PGC-1 α . As animals age, levels of PGC-1 α tend to decline, which means cells gradually lose the ability to replenish their mitochondrial supply [15,16]. Reduced mitochondrial mass contributes directly to fatigue, muscle weakness, cognitive decline, and impaired tissue repair, all hallmarks of biological aging.

TFAM encodes Mitochondrial Transcription Factor A, a protein that lives inside mitochondria and is responsible for copying, maintaining, and protecting mitochondrial DNA. TFAM acts as a first line guardian, binding to mitochondrial DNA and shielding it from the reactive oxygen species that are an unavoidable byproduct of energy production. Maintaining or increasing TFAM expression is therefore a meaningful indicator of mitochondrial stability and genomic integrity in aging organisms [17,18].

SIRT1 encodes Sirtuin 1, a protein that belongs to a family of enzymes closely associated with longevity across multiple species [19]. SIRT1 is activated when cellular NAD⁺ levels are high, a condition that signals metabolic efficiency and low caloric intake, two states strongly associated with healthy aging and lifespan extension. Once activated, SIRT1 modifies hundreds of target proteins, helping to reduce inflammation, improve insulin sensitivity, promote DNA repair, and enhance mitochondrial quality control.

SIRT3 encodes Sirtuin 3, which works specifically inside the mitochondria rather than the cell nucleus. Mitochondria produce reactive oxygen species as a natural byproduct of energy generation, and without adequate antioxidant protection, these molecules damage proteins, lipids, and DNA within the mitochondria themselves. SIRT3 helps neutralize this damage by activating key antioxidant enzymes, including manganese superoxide dismutase (SOD2) [20]. Increased SIRT3 expression is associated with reduced mitochondrial stress, improved cellular energy production, and in multiple studies longer health span [21].

PRKAA1 encodes the alpha-1 subunit of AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), which monitors the ratio of AMP to ATP inside cells, a direct readout of whether the cell has enough energy or is under metabolic stress. When energy is low, AMPK activates a cascade of adaptive responses: it promotes mitochondrial biogenesis, increases fatty acid oxidation, suppresses inflammatory signaling, and inhibits energy wasting processes. AMPK is also the primary target of metformin, the most widely prescribed diabetes drug and one of the most intensively studied potential anti-aging compounds.

This pilot study identified a preliminary systemic molecular response to jugular applied coherent laser LLLT in a subset of geriatric Beagle dogs. The use of whole blood gene expression as the primary readout is a critical design feature: because whole blood reflects contributions from multiple circulating cell populations, changes in this compartment represent an organism level, systemic signal rather than a localized tissue response. The most responsive animals demonstrated coordinated upregulation of PPARGC1A, TFAM, SIRT1, SIRT3, and PRKAA1, the value of this pattern lies not in any single gene but in their coordinated movement. When these five genes increase together in circulating blood cells, it suggests that the organism has engaged a broader mitochondrial health network, not merely one component of it. This coordinated signature aligns with pathways associated with maintenance of cellular energetic capacity, metabolic flexibility, and redox homeostasis across tissues, features that are central to healthier aging trajectories in mammals.

The strongest individual signals were seen in PPARGC1A and TFAM. PPARGC1A is the master upstream regulator of the mitochondrial biogenesis cascade; TFAM is its downstream effector responsible for maintaining the mitochondrial genome itself. Their co-elevation suggests that the biogenesis program was engaged at multiple levels rather than at a single step. The accompanying increases in SIRT1 and SIRT3 further indicate that the cellular stress adaptation and redox protection arms of the mitochondrial health network were also activated. PRKAA1 upregulation adds an energy sensing dimension: AMPK activation is associated with suppression of inflammatory signaling, improved metabolic efficiency, and longevity pathways across species, and is the primary mechanism of action of metformin, a widely studied anti-aging compound [22].

Importantly, these data should not be interpreted as proof that LLLT reverses aging or extends lifespan. Rather, the observed gene expression pattern is best characterized as a systemic molecular signature consistent with activation of pathways that biology has repeatedly associated with healthier aging. The study did not assess functional aging outcomes, epigenetic age, frailty, cognition, or longevity. What it does show is that a wearable, noninvasive jugular laser device can produce a coherent, multi-gene, whole blood molecular response in aging animals, and that this response aligns directionally with the molecular hallmarks of better mitochondrial health.

The mechanistic basis for a systemic response following localized jugular irradiation can be described through two complementary pathways. First, LLLT may directly modulate mitochondrial function and signaling in cells residing within irradiated neck tissues, including vascular endothelial cells, immune cells, and perivascular tissue. Second, and particularly relevant to the jugular application site, the intervention may influence circulating mitochondrial cargo as blood passes through the illuminated region. Emerging evidence has established that the extracellular compartment contains free floating mitochondria and mitochondria derived vesicles carrying mitochondrial proteins, lipids, peptides, and nucleic acids [23]. These structures are recognized as mediators of intercellular communication and mitochondrial quality control [24]. Light induced modulation of these circulating components represents a biologically plausible mechanism by which localized jugular irradiation could engage systemic mitochondrial signaling a mechanism consistent with both the whole blood readout and the persistence of effects two weeks after treatment cessation. This proposed pathway remains inferential in the present study, as circulating extracellular mitochondrial components were not directly measured.

The response heterogeneity itself is informative. FTB01 and POA04 were clearly more responsive than TNH02 and LUF05, with GUR03 intermediate. Notably, the two least responsive animals had documented comorbidities (diabetes mellitus, hypercapnia, ehrlichiosis) that may have reduced baseline mitochondrial responsiveness or created systemic inflammatory or metabolic noise that attenuated the signal. This suggests that future studies should stratify analyses by baseline health status and consider that the benefits of LLLT on mitochondrial gene expression may be greatest in animals with preserved physiological reserves [25,26].

This study was limited by a small sample size, the absence of a sham treated control group, and a short follow up period. These limitations are acknowledged. Despite these constraints, the study achieves its goal: it demonstrates that repeated wearable jugular LLLT is feasible in geriatric dogs and, in a subset of individuals, produces a coherent, directionally consistent, multi-gene systemic molecular response aligned with healthy aging biology. These findings justify larger controlled studies incorporating sham treatment, longer treatment duration, functional aging outcomes, inflammatory and metabolic biomarkers, and epigenetic aging measures.

Conclusion

Wearable jugular applied coherent laser LLLT was feasible and well tolerated in this small cohort of geriatric dogs. Three of five animals demonstrated positive directional changes across the full gene panel, with the most responsive subset showing coordinated increases in PPARGC1A, TFAM, SIRT1, SIRT3, and PRKAA1, a whole blood molecular pattern consistent with systemic activation of

mitochondrial biogenesis, redox protection, and energy-sensing pathways relevant to healthy aging. These preliminary findings support further controlled investigation of jugular LLLT as a strategy to engage systemic mitochondrial health pathways in aging animals.

Approval of Ethical Commission

Formal ethical committee approval was not required for this study because the procedures were non-invasive and conducted within routine animal care conditions, without surgical or pharmacologic intervention. All procedures were performed at the National Center for Laboratory Animal Production (CENPALAB) in accordance with applicable institutional animal welfare and handling standards.

Conflict of Interest

TS is an employee of Erchonia Corporation, which sponsored the study. Erchonia Corporation provided the LLLT device used in the study and was responsible for supplying the study protocol and device-use training. The study procedures and data collection were performed independently at CENPALAB at the National Center for Laboratory Animal Production (CENPALAB). No other conflicts of interest were declared.

Author's Contribution

RS and TS: writing original draft preparation. All authors have read and approved to the final version of the manuscript.

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